

Supplemental Materials

Table S1. Variable measures and data sources

Abbreviation	Variable	Measurement	Data Source
<i>dr</i>	ESG Disclosure Regulations	Binary variable: 2 for firms required to issue a mandatory ESG report; 1 for firms issuing ESG reports voluntarily	CSMAR database
<i>gp</i>	Government Penalties	Number of government penalties	Corporate annual report
<i>gpp</i>	Government Procurement Projects	Number of government procurement contracts secured by the company	China Government Procurement Network
<i>gs</i>	Government Subsidies	Amount of government subsidies	Corporate annual report
<i>esgc</i>	ESG Best Practice Case Collection	Three-tier variable: 0 for all companies before 2021; after 2021, 2 for companies selected as exemplary cases, 1 for non-selected firms	China Association for Public Companies
<i>pg</i>	Peer ESG rating gaps	Ln (1+difference in ESG rating scores relative to industry-leading firms)	Huazheng rating
<i>ei</i>	ESG integration	Co-occurrence frequency of “ESG”-related and “integration”-related lexicons in annual reports	Corporate annual report
<i>mc</i>	Manager cognition of the ESG-firm performance link	Co-occurrence frequency of “ESG”-related and “corporate performance”-related lexicons in annual reports	Corporate annual report
<i>age</i>	Firm Age	Years since establishment	CSMAR database
<i>lev</i>	Asset-Liability Ratio	Total liabilities divided by total assets	CSMAR database
<i>roe</i>	Return on Equity	Net income divided by average shareholders' equity	CSMAR database
<i>esgf</i>	ESG Funding	Binary variable: 0 = No, 1 = Yes	CSMAR database
<i>top1</i>	Ownership concentration	Shareholding ratio of the largest shareholder	CSMAR database
<i>board</i>	Board size	Number of board members	CSMAR database
<i>indep</i>	Independent directors	Proportion of independent directors on the board	CSMAR database
<i>female</i>	Female directors	Proportion of female directors on the board	CSMAR database
<i>dual</i>	CEO-Chairman duality	Binary variable: 0 = No, 1 = Yes	CSMAR database

Table S2. Lexicon related to ESG, integration, and corporate performance

Concept	Concept-related lexicon
ESG	Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG); Environmental protection; Social responsibility; Governance; Stakeholders; Ecology; Green; Protection; Energy conservation; Carbon peak; Carbon emissions; Clean energy; Climate change; Water resources; Waste; Noise; Pollution; Environmental certification; Low-carbon; Renewable energy; Accidents; Safety; Quality management; Employees; Suppliers; Contractors; Subcontractors; Supply chain; Human rights; Fairness; Equity; Rural revitalization; Innovation; Technology; Transparency; Board diversity; Corruption; Integrity; Compliance; Compensation; Remuneration; Governance structure
Integration	Strategy; Strategic; Path; Planning; Mission; Vision; Management; Development; Direction; Target; Positioning; Method; Regulation; System; Training; Link; Evaluation; Assessment; Appraisal; Reward and punishment; Negative list; Implementation; Improve; Incentive; Committee; Manager; Access; Punishment; Unqualified; Digital; Adhere; Persist; Extend; Approach; Tool; Practice; Emphasize; Cross-departmental; Concept; Operation; Best; Case; Excellent; Integrate; Incorporate
Corporate performance	Image; Credibility; Reputation; Recognition; Market; Return; Profitability; Approval; Efficiency; Important; Development; Sustainable; Strategy; Transformation; Stable; Level; Influence; Trust; Enhance; Investors; Risk management; Risk control; Risk response; Confidence; Satisfaction; Status; Benefits; Operation; Management

Table S3. Examples of ESG integration

Stock symbol (example sources)	Examples of sentences
601390 (2023 Annual report)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrated ESG elements into medium- and long-term planning for sustainable development, governance enhancement, and business development. • The Board of Directors fully supervises, manages, and oversees the company’s ESG issues, risks, and opportunities, and approves ESG reports. • Published Guidelines for High-Standard ESG Performance to establish institutional frameworks supporting the company’s commitment to social responsibility excellence. It has also established cross-departmental cooperation mechanisms to ensure the accuracy, reliability, and timeliness of sustainability initiatives.
601668 (2023 Annual report)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developed the “China State Construction ESG Work Plan” to strengthen ESG governance and advance initiative implementation. • Using ESG as a key strategic driver, we integrated its principles into our “166” strategic roadmap, established robust ESG governance mechanisms, and aligned ESG with operations. We won the China ESG Excellence Practice Award. • The key responsibilities of the Board of Directors and the Strategic and Investment Committee are to ensure the seamless integration of ESG principles into the overall corporate strategy. This initiative seeks to foster a more independent, efficient, and professional approach to ESG management within the Board. Six meetings were held to discuss ESG-related resolutions, and eight ESG-related topics were reviewed. • Integrated ESG metrics into management compensation assessments. • We listen to stakeholder opinions to strengthen ESG management. We survey management, employees, investors, suppliers, partners, and community representatives, and collect 1,555 valid responses to develop the 2023 ESG Materiality Matrix and address stakeholder concerns. • We continue to advance green building certification work, with numerous new construction and operational projects receiving domestic green building ratings. We complete over 2,000 green building certification projects. • Established a sustainable supply chain system. All approved suppliers must hold the required quality, safety, environmental certifications, and licenses. Prioritized those with strong reputations, governance, and green certifications; avoided partners with serious negative records. Maintained a non-compliant supplier blacklist. For suppliers with substandard products, safety incidents, or misconduct (dishonesty, fraud, corruption), we impose one-year transaction bans, two-year regional procurement exclusions, and exit mechanisms.
601800 (2023 Annual report)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Board’s Strategy, Investment, and ESG Committee integrated safety, technology, quality management, and environmental performance into executive evaluations to support ESG strategy development. • We conduct annual ESG training to track trends, disseminate updates, and enhance employees’ ESG understanding, capabilities, and expertise.
601117 (2023 Annual report)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We have strategically expanded our core business to cover environmental markets, including chemical wastewater and hazardous waste management projects. • This swift expansion has secured numerous environmental project contracts.
601669 (2023 Annual report)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We organize the selection of green construction demonstration projects to promote the effective implementation of management systems and standards.
600170 (2022 Annual Report)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We remain committed to clean and green production, and embrace digital and intelligent concepts to develop innovative ready-mixed concrete with corresponding production processes.
601618 (2022 Annual Report)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We establish a Board Sustainability Committee and formulate its Working Rules to strengthen strategic focus and research on occupational health, safety, environmental protection, ESG, and sustainability. • The company was selected for the inaugural Forbes China ESG50 list, recognized as an “Outstanding ESG Practice Case for Listed Companies” by the CAPCO, and awarded CAPCO’s “Best Practice for 2021 Annual Report Performance Briefing”.
000065 (2023 Annual report)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We strengthen supply chain ESG management, regularly training suppliers on quality, safety, environmental protection, and social responsibility.

Table S4. Examples of managerial cognition of the ESG-firm performance link

Stock symbol (example sources)	Examples of sentences
601390 (2023 Annual report)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The board believes managing ESG risks and opportunities is crucial for the company’s high-quality, sustainable development.• We have published our 15th ESG report, which won high praise from the Shanghai and Hong Kong capital markets.• The case “Committed to Becoming a Practitioner of International ESG Standards” received CAPCO’s Best Practice Award and China Enterprise Reform and Development Research Association’s Outstanding ESG Case Award, boosting the company’s capital market value.
601668 (2023 Annual report)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The board highly recognizes ESG’s significance for the company’s long-term stable operation.• The board recognizes the significant impact of ESG governance risks on the company, regularly conducting ESG assessments based on the external socio-economic environment and corporate strategy. It uses assessment results as key management/improvement areas, integrating them into the overall strategy for supervision and enhancement.• By improving its ESG governance system and enhancing ESG performance, the company strengthens its responsible public listed company image.• We recognize that exploring carbon reduction pathways, developing efficient emission reduction technologies, and implementing effective emission reduction measures are essential steps toward achieving green transformation and sustainable development.• We voluntarily disclose ESG and other investor-relevant information for value assessment and investment decisions.
002051 (2023 Annual report)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• To enhance ESG management capabilities, we have established and refined our ESG management framework by setting up a Strategy and ESG Committee under the Board of Directors, strengthening core competitiveness and sustainability.• We enhance our ESG governance structure and capabilities to promote high-quality development of three core businesses.
601800 (2023 Annual report)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• ESG compliance is vital for companies to adapt to global economic shifts and address high-quality development challenges.
601868 (2023 Annual report)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• We scientifically understand the relationship between ESG and sustainable development, effectively manage corporate social and environmental impact, foster a positive cycle between business growth and responsibility fulfillment, and endeavor to be a model for corporate social responsibility.
002116 (2023 Annual report)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• To ensure effective implementation of major ESG matters, all business and functional departments integrate critical areas into their daily operations, seeking improvement opportunities to underpin corporate sustainability.
600248 (2023 Annual report)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• In pursuit of long-term sustainable development, the company undertakes its ESG responsibilities and continuously promotes the harmonious alignment of economic, social, and environmental benefits.
000065 (2023 Annual report)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Focused on sustainability management, the company integrates ESG into its operations and manages ESG-related risks, thereby continuously elevating its corporate governance performance.

Table S5. Descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation matrix (N = 343)

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17
1. <i>dr</i>	1.000																
2. <i>gp</i>	0.473***	1.000															
3. <i>gpp</i>	0.534***	0.410***	1.000														
4. <i>gs</i>	0.575***	0.421***	0.644***	1.000													
5. <i>pg</i>	-0.419***	-0.217***	-0.396***	-0.464***	1.000												
6. <i>esgc</i>	0.077	0.110*	0.231***	0.238***	-0.243***	1.000											
7. <i>mc</i>	0.015	-0.033	0.062	0.100	-0.137*	0.209***	1.000										
8. <i>age</i>	-0.562***	-0.355***	-0.312***	-0.366***	0.372***	0.109*	-0.213***	1.000									
9. <i>lev</i>	0.165**	0.246***	0.199***	0.238***	0.008	0.099	0.015	-0.092	1.000								
10. <i>roe</i>	0.065	0.085	0.085	0.082	-0.093	-0.124*	-0.064	-0.061	-0.059	1.000							
11. <i>esgf</i>	0.554***	0.400***	0.505***	0.555***	-0.349***	0.047	0.051	-0.421***	0.198***	0.080	1.000						
12. <i>top1</i>	0.345***	0.301***	0.267***	0.206***	-0.248***	0.033	0.000	-0.351***	0.331***	0.158**	0.235***	1.000					
13. <i>board</i>	-0.146**	-0.107*	-0.083	-0.035	0.104	0.066	0.118*	0.140**	0.233***	-0.208***	-0.059	-0.009	1.000				
14. <i>indep</i>	0.249***	0.411***	0.226***	0.261***	-0.161**	0.108*	0.036	-0.230***	0.031	0.082	0.262***	0.110*	-0.280***	1.000			
15. <i>female</i>	-0.280***	-0.250***	-0.179***	-0.189***	0.221***	0.014	-0.080	0.369***	-0.258***	-0.069	-0.230***	-0.254***	0.057	-0.236***	1.000		
16. <i>dual</i>	-0.138*	-0.102	-0.096	-0.012	0.055	-0.022	-0.106*	0.038	-0.219***	0.033	-0.067	-0.197***	-0.047	-0.043	0.022	1.000	
17. <i>ei</i>	0.140**	0.085	0.142**	0.202***	-0.259***	0.223***	0.843***	-0.259***	0.017	-0.061	0.155**	0.115*	0.107*	0.081	-0.154**	-0.122*	1.000
Mean	1.207	6.140	6.289	10668.390	2.337	0.382	101.192	22.531	0.689	0.038	0.303	37.937	10.636	0.381	0.123	0.172	124.554
SD	0.406	14.136	13.539	24392.340	0.641	0.549	48.956	6.306	0.147	0.244	0.461	15.820	2.873	0.089	0.115	0.378	52.176
Min	1.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35	8.000	0.139	-2.772	0.000	4.419	5.000	0.214	0.000	0.000	43.000
Max	2.000	149.000	73.000	147372.90	3.573	2.000	347	39.000	0.954	0.268	1.000	78.588	23.000	0.750	0.500	1.000	364.000

Note: *, **, *** indicate significance at the 5%, 1%, and 0.1% levels, respectively. Variable abbreviations: *dr* = ESG disclosure regulations; *gp* = government penalties; *gpp* = government procurement projects; *gs* = government subsidies; *esgc* = ESG best practice case collection; *pg* = peer ESG rating gaps; *ei* = ESG integration; *mc* = managerial cognition of the ESG-firm performance link; *age* = firm age; *lev* = asset-liability ratio; *roe* = return on equity; *esgf* = ESG funding; *top1* = ownership concentration; *board* = board size; *indep* = independent directors; *female* = female directors; *dual* = CEO-chairman duality.

Table S6. Robustness test of replacing dependent variable

Variables	<i>Wind ESG rating</i>								
	Model 7	Model 8	Model 9	Model 10	Model 11	Model 12	Model 13	Model 14	Model 15
<i>dr</i>	0.299 (0.207)		0.292 (0.208)						
<i>gp</i>		-0.002 (0.004)	-0.001 (0.004)						
<i>gpp</i>				0.010* (0.004)			0.009* (0.004)		
<i>gs</i>					0.000* (0.000)		0.000* (0.000)		
<i>esgc</i>						0.641*** (0.170)	0.521** (0.189)		
<i>pg</i>								-0.025* (0.011)	
<i>mc</i>									0.003** (0.001)
<i>Constant</i>	2.512*** (0.632)	3.124*** (0.592)	2.538*** (0.637)	3.197*** (0.585)	3.202*** (0.585)	5.955*** (0.952)	5.499*** (1.002)	3.191*** (0.665)	3.163*** (0.584)
<i>controls</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Firm FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
R ²	0.343	0.329	0.345	0.343	0.344	0.363	0.371	0.329	0.344
N	343	343	343	343	343	343	343	343	343
F-statistic	12.35	12.47	12.78	12.48	12.49	12.72	12.61	12.87	13.26

Note: Standard errors in parentheses. +, *, **, *** indicate significance at the 10%, 5%, 1%, and 0.1% levels, respectively. All models include firm and year fixed effects. FE = fixed effects. Variable abbreviations: *dr* = ESG disclosure regulations; *gp* = government penalties; *gpp* = government procurement projects; *gs* = government subsidies; *esgc* = ESG best practice case collection; *pg* = peer ESG rating gaps; *mc* = managerial cognition. Control variables are included but not reported for brevity.

Table S7. Robustness test of a two-year lag for all independent and control variables

Variables	<i>ei</i>								
	Model 7	Model 8	Model 9	Model 10	Model 11	Model 12	Model 13	Model 14	Model 15
<i>dr</i>	2.201 (8.883)		1.576 (9.493)						
<i>gp</i>		-0.241 (0.167)	-0.239 (0.201)						
<i>gpp</i>				0.469* (0.220)			0.475* (0.231)		
<i>gs</i>					0.000* (0.000)		0.000* (0.000)		
<i>esgc</i>						17.879* (8.764)	17.749* (8.964)		
<i>pg</i>								-8.072* (3.763)	
<i>mc</i>									0.191*** (0.056)
<i>Constant</i>	-29.550 (26.028)	-28.395 (23.795)	-26.658 (27.145)	-27.269 (23.660)	-27.695 (23.992)	64.270 (54.163)	62.183 (55.294)	-20.213 (26.313)	-26.349 (23.932)
<i>controls</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Firm FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
R ²	0.409	0.415	0.424	0.422	0.409	0.419	0.431	0.410	0.412
N	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281
F-statistic	11.07	11.34	11.21	11.66	11.07	11.54	11.38	11.13	11.19

Note: Standard errors in parentheses. +, *, **, *** indicate significance at the 10%, 5%, 1%, and 0.1% levels, respectively. All models include firm and year fixed effects. FE = fixed effects. Variable abbreviations: *dr* = ESG disclosure regulations; *gp* = government penalties; *gpp* = government procurement projects; *gs* = government subsidies; *esgc* = ESG best practice case collection; *pg* = peer ESG rating gaps; *ei* = ESG integration; *mc* = managerial cognition. Control variables are included but not reported for brevity.

Table S8. Robustness test of the baseline model using clustered robust standard errors

Variables	<i>mc</i>								<i>ei</i>								
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6	Model 7	Model 8	Model 9	Model 10	Model 11	Model 12	Model 13	Model 14	Model 15	Model 16	Model 17
<i>dr</i>	8.547 (5.710)		6.477 (4.900)						2.780 (7.529)		1.836 (7.484)						
<i>gp</i>		-0.456*** (0.110)	-0.445*** (0.112)							-0.206 (0.198)	-0.203 (0.199)						
<i>gpp</i>				0.544*** (0.156)			0.497** (0.180)					0.374* (0.187)				0.353+ (0.207)	
<i>gs</i>					0.000** (0.000)		0.000** (0.000)						0.000* (0.000)			0.000* (0.000)	
<i>esgc</i>						21.429*** (5.080)	20.724*** (5.938)							19.779** (7.412)	18.843* (7.754)		
<i>pg</i>								-0.130 (3.330)									-6.730* (3.252)
<i>mc</i>																	0.182* (0.080)
<i>Constant</i>	-30.156 (26.282)	-14.247 (24.748)	-21.946 (25.376)	-14.629 (26.277)	-16.135 (26.305)	75.432* (38.106)	46.752 (40.870)	-19.676 (28.135)	-51.061 (33.162)	-45.137 (32.017)	-47.320 (32.596)	-43.995 (31.983)	-44.705 (32.528)	40.435 (49.626)	23.727 (51.163)	-21.630 (36.293)	-44.136 (30.480)
<i>controls</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Firm FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
R ²	0.249	0.265	0.267	0.271	0.259	0.268	0.296	0.247	0.408	0.412	0.416	0.421	0.416	0.428	0.483	0.419	0.450
N	343	343	343	343	343	343	343	343	343	343	343	343	343	343	343	343	343
F-statistic	5.15	8.71	8.09	8.43	7.73	14.58	11.12	4.69	7.28	7.33	7.47	7.00	6.64	8.41	8.29	7.05	8.96

Note: Clustered robust standard errors in parentheses. +, *, **, *** indicate significance at the 10%, 5%, 1%, and 0.1% levels, respectively. All models include firm and year fixed effects. FE = fixed effects. Variable abbreviations: *dr* = ESG disclosure regulations; *gp* = government penalties; *gpp* = government procurement projects; *gs* = government subsidies; *esgc* = ESG best practice case collection; *pg* = peer ESG rating gaps; *ei* = ESG integration; *mc* = managerial cognition. Control variables are included but not reported for brevity.